

HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM AND THE SCIENCE OF PEDAGOGICS IN UZBEKISTAN BETWEEN 1917-1991

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Abstract. *In this article, between 1917-1991, the development of the education system and the science of pedagogy in Uzbekistan was under the pressure of the communist ideology, our national values were trampled, and despite this, many outstanding scientists from our country grew up and conducted scientific research in the field of pedagogy and It is stated that they have made great contributions to the field of education.*

Keywords: *October Night, Civil War, eavesdropping company, Stalin's repressions, Uzbek pedagogy, Marx-Lenin theory*

When talking about the period of 1917-1990, it is appropriate to mention the following thoughts of the first President:

"... 130 years ago, our people lost their national independence and historical statehood and fell into colonialism. During this period, our ancestors and our nation went through difficult trials and struggles. Our ancestors endured the tyranny of Russia. Our fathers directly experienced the events of the October Night, the Civil War, the eavesdropping company, Stalin's repressions, the sufferings of the Second World War, the dangerous fifties and finally the eighties, which were named "the tyranny of the paratroopers". "We also saw the period called, we lived under the dominant pressure of the communist ideology. We know very well that this ideology is based on oppression and violence, greed and fraud. That's why it fell" [1]

The oppression and complications of this colonial policy had an impact on our spheres of education and national identity.[2]

During the former Soviet regime, the science of pedagogy was formed on a completely different basis. It was an integral part of former Soviet pedagogy. Russian pedagogy textbooks written by Russian scientists were used. As a result, Uzbek pedagogy turned into a fake science formed within the Marxian-Leninist theory.

After the October uprising, instead of 3 khanates, the Turkestan Mukhtar Republic, Bukhara and Khiva People's Republics based on a new ideology were established. [3]

The content of educational work in schools has changed based on the purpose of the system. Attention to religion and the Holy Qur'an was completely forbidden. In 1918 - 20, based on the new policy, curricula and programs were created, lessons and events were held on this basis. Events were distorted in history classes. In literature classes, attention was paid to teaching Russian writers. The scale of teaching specific subjects has expanded. There have been changes in the teaching of social sciences.

First of all, the shortage of teachers in national schools was noticed. On January 20, 1918, on the basis of the decree of the former RSFSR Central Committee on "Separation of the Church from the State and the School from the Church", various mullahs and religious intellectuals were not allowed to teach in schools. [4]

In response to the government's new policy in the field of public education, many schools were opened in the country, and the number of students increased significantly. In 1918, in Tashkent, the consciousness of the country's educational workers was opened, and measures were set for the reconstruction of public education. The so-called "labor schools" were opened. New types of schools began to emerge. By the spring of 1918, the number of schools operating in the republic reached 330.

At the beginning of the 1919-20 academic year, 350 schools worked in Fergana region, 839 in Syrdarya region, and 216 in Samarkand region.

Girls' schools began to open. In 1917, Bashorat Jalilova opened a school in Zevak neighborhood of Beshyogoch and taught 22 Uzbek girls. Then the number of such schools will increase.

Secondary, special secondary and higher educational institutions have also started to open in the country. In 1918-1920, the Institute of Oriental Studies of Turkestan, Timiryazev Institute of Education, Khotin - Girls' Institute of Education, etc., in 1921, Institute of Chemistry - Pharmacology, Conservatory, 6 Agricultural Technical Colleges were opened. Among them, the People's University of Turkestan, opened in Toshket on April 21, 1918, was of special importance. Its branches will be established in the regions. The State University of Turkestan was established on the basis of this university by the decree of the former RSFSR Central Committee on September 7, 1920. [5]

Pedagogical educational institutions - pedagogical technical schools were opened. But the lack of teaching staff was a big problem. By 1920, 1200 teachers were trained.

In 1920, 7 educational institutes (inpros) were established and 1145 students were admitted to them. In the 1921-22 academic year, 2403 schools and other children's institutions worked in the country, and 170105 children studied in them.

In 1924, after the demarcation of the state and the formation of the former Soviet republics, in order to achieve economic, social and cultural superiority in the republics, it was necessary to involve children in general education and to end the new generation of illiteracy among adults. Therefore, on August 14, 1930, the decision "On general compulsory primary education" was adopted by the former USSR Ministry of Education and Culture. In it, 8-10-year-old children should be included in general compulsory education for at least a 4-year course of primary schools, 11-15-year-olds should be organized for accelerated 1-2-year courses for those who did not study in the 4-year course of the labor school, in industrial cities 1930-31 issues of attracting children to the 7-year compulsory school from the academic year were considered.

In 1929, the Latin alphabet was adopted instead of the Arabic alphabet in Uzbekistan.

On September 5, 1931, the decision "On Primary and Secondary Schools" pointed out the shortcomings, and paid attention to improving the method of organizing and conducting lessons. Issues of organizing cycle associations and pedagogical associations were discussed.

New educational programs were created. On August 25, 1932, the decision of the former Central Committee of the CPSU (b) "On the curriculum and regime of primary and secondary schools" was issued. [6]

In 1933, the decision on "Primary and secondary school textbooks" was issued, the creation of rapidly changing textbooks was condemned.

From 1933, tests of transfer from class to class were introduced.

Since 1934, the role of class leader was established in schools.

Pedagogical textbooks began to be created. In 1932-40, textbooks and manuals for higher and secondary educational institutions of pedagogy by A. Afrikanov, P. Gruzdev, I. Kairov, B. Yesipov were published.

In 1940, the 1st meeting of teachers of the republic was held in Tashkent. The issues of improving education, implementation of compulsory secondary education were discussed. In May 1940, at the 3rd session of the Supreme Soviet of the former USSR, the law "On transferring the Uzbek script from the Latinized alphabet to the new Uzbek alphabet based on Russian graphics" was adopted.

High and medium special pad. the number of educational institutions increased. In the years 1933-37, 26 pedagogic schools, 5 rabfaks, Central Asian State University, Samarkand DU named after Navoi, Tashkent, Fergana, and Bukhara pedagogic institutes operated in the republic. During these times, as a result of the government's policy in the field of education, the Uzbek people were deprived of the opportunity to learn and learn about their history, national customs, traditions, and universal human values. the righteous suffered in exile.

During the war, all material resources and moral forces of the people were drawn to the front. Uzbekistan also contributed to the defense.

Many production enterprises in the lands occupied by the enemy were moved to Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan provided them with a place and labor force. He contributed to providing the army with food and clothing. During the war, there were difficulties in the field of education as well as in all fields. [7]

Many teachers were drafted into the army, school buildings were turned into hospitals, and there was a shortage of school supplies.

Educational programs were adapted to the conditions. In 1943, a decision was made to take into account children aged 8 to 15 and take them to compulsory education. Separate education of boys and girls was also introduced this year. The number of girls attending school has increased.

The number of people evacuated to Uzbekistan increased. They reached 716 thousand in 1942. There were 154 orphanages in 1943 and 242 in 1945.

Due to the difficulties of the war period, studies were conducted in 3 shifts, the lessons were 40 minutes long, singing and painting lessons were not held. The number of teachers decreased, and great attention was paid to the training of teachers from women and girls. Another difficulty was transferred to Russian graphics before the war, but it had not yet been overcome, the books had not been published.

Since 1944, children's knowledge and behavior have been evaluated based on a 5-point system.

After the war, measures were taken to improve public education. In 1949, general compulsory 7-year education was introduced. The number of technical schools has been increased for the purpose of vocational training. Boarding schools were established in 1956.

The demand for teachers has increased. Since 1953, pedbilimyurtlari has been working on the basis of high school, the duration of study was 2 years. Since 1952, teachers' institutes have been transformed into pedagogic institutes.

From the 1962-63 academic year, 7-year schools were reorganized and turned into 8-year schools.

In 1962, for the first time under ToshSU, the United Soviet for granting scientific degrees in pedagogic sciences was established. In spite of all the obstacles in the government policy during

the recession years, within the existing possibilities, the research of the pedagogical ideas of the great thinkers of Central Asia, including Uzbek intellectuals, poets and scientists continued. [8]

In the 1960s and 1970s, the opinions of our scholars such as Furqat, Sadridin Ainiy, Alisher Navoi, Jami and Davani, Abdulla Avloni [9] were studied. "Kalila and Dimna", "Nightmare" were published. The well-known pedagogue scientist Z. Mirtursunov studied our folk pedagogy for the first time in his work "Uzbek folk pedagogy and its reflection in folk oral creativity" (1967).

In the 1970s and 1980s, general education schools, which occupied an important place in the education system, served the ideological and cultural tasks of the state. In 1972, by the government, "On completing the transfer of young people to general secondary education and further development of general education schools". The transfer of young people to general secondary education was completed by 1975.

In the 1975-76 academic year, there were 9,642 secondary schools in rural and urban areas of Uzbekistan, where 237,500 teachers taught 38,028,000 students.

In this academic year, 246,400 students were educated in 42 higher educational institutions, 400 doctors of science and more than 5,000 candidates of science worked in them.

More than 900,000 children are involved in pre-school educational institutions.

More than 440,000 children were taken to non-school educational institutions.

By the 1980s, the shortcomings of society in many areas were noticed, and large-scale reconstruction work was started.

In 1984, the Government's "Main Directions for General Education and Vocational School Reform" was approved.

Uzbek pedagogy did not stop growing completely. Many of our scientists worked tirelessly for its rise. Siddiq Rajabov (1910-1993) was especially devoted to the development of Uzbek pedagogy in the 1970s. Works in Scientific Research and Chartered TSPI. He defends his doctoral dissertation on the topic "History of Uzbekistan's schools". Dozens of works such as "Some issues of the development of the science of pedagogy", "Classical teaching in education and training", "Didactics of higher education" are published.

Malla Ochilov (1931) made a great contribution to the development of the science of pedagogy. His treatises such as "Ethics of a teacher", "Process of moral education of students", "Ethical formation of a future teacher", scientific research works of students" are famous. He published the work of the Czech pedagogue Ya. A. Komensky "Great didactics" in the 1st edition. and translated it into Uzbek.

In the 1980s, Muzaffar Abdullayev's (1931) comments about Farobi's views caused pedagogy to rise to a new level. O.Sharoffidinov, I.Husankhojayev, Z.Mirtursinov, R.Usmanov and other scientists wrote the books "Abu Nasr Farobi", "Farobi and his treatises", "Farobi on education" fought in

In short, despite the development of the education system and pedagogy in Uzbekistan, and the prevailing pressure of the communist ideology, many great scientists from our country grew up and created effectively between 1917-1991. They conducted scientific research in the field of pedagogy and made a great contribution to the field of education.

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